

On The Diophantine Equation $\sum x_i^2 + a = y^2$ And

$$\sum x_i^3 + a = y^3$$

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Abstract:

In this paper, the Diophantine equations $\sum x_i^2 + a = y^2$ and $\sum x_i^3 + a = y^3$ where $x_1 \neq x_2 \neq x_3 \neq \dots$ and a is a positive integer have been discussed for possible positive integral solutions.

Keywords: Diophantine equation and integral solution.

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1 Introduction:

Several researchers have discussed the non-linear Diophantine equations. Most famous non-linear Diophantine equations are **Fermat's Last Problem** (1637) and **Beal's Conjecture** (1993). Fermat's Last Problem was solved by **Andrew Wiles** (1995). Beal's Conjecture is still an open unsolved problem. **Gandhi & Sarma** (2013) attempted to disprove the Beal's conjecture. **Gregorio, L.T.D.** (2013) presented a proof for the the Beal's conjecture and a new proof for the Fermat's last theorem.

Gola, L.W. (2014) presented a proof of Beal's conjecture. **Ghanouchi, J.** (2014) presented an elementary proof of Fermat-Wiles theorem and generalization to Beal's conjecture. **Thiagrajan, R.C.** (2014) provided computational results and a proof of Beal's conjecture.

In this paper, we have discussed the Diophantine equations $\sum x_i^2 + a = y^2$ and $\sum x_i^3 + a = y^3$ where $x_1 \neq x_2 \neq x_3 \neq \dots$ and a is a positive integer. The physical interpretation of first Diophantine equation is that some squares of different dimensions and a strip of dimension $a \times 1$ is equal to a big square while the physical interpretation of second Diophantine equation is that some cubes of different dimensions and solid strip of dimensions $a \times 1 \times 1$ is equal to a big cube.

2 Analysis: (A) Diophantine equation $\sum x_i^2 + a = y^2$: This Diophantine equation will be discussed for $a = 10, 20, 30, 40, 50$ and 60 .

(a) For $a = 10$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^2 + 10 = y^2. \quad \dots(1)$$

- (i) If we take $x_1 = 3$, $x_2 = 9$ and $y = 10$ then equation (1) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (3, 9, 10)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 10 = y^2$.
- (ii) If we take $x_1 = 1$, $x_2 = 2$, $x_3 = 3$, $x_4 = 5$ and $y = 7$ then equation (1) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (1, 2, 3, 5, 7)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 + 10 = y^2$.
- (iii) If we take $x_1 = 2$, $x_2 = 3$, $x_3 = 4$, $x_4 = 5$ and $y = 8$ then equation (1) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (2, 3, 4, 5, 8)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 + 10 = y^2$.

(b) For $a = 20$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^2 + 20 = y^2. \quad \dots(2)$$

- (i) If we take $x_1 = 7$, $x_2 = 10$ and $y = 13$ then equation (2) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (7, 10, 13)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 20 = y^2$.
- (ii) If we take $x_1 = 4$, $x_2 = 8$ and $y = 10$ then equation (2) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (4, 8, 10)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 20 = y^2$.
- (iii) If we take $x_1 = 6$, $x_2 = 7$, $x_3 = 8$ and $y = 13$ then equation (2) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (6, 7, 8, 13)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 20 = y^2$.
- (iv) If we take $x_1 = 6$, $x_2 = 13$ and $y = 15$ then equation (2) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (6, 13, 15)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 20 = y^2$.

(c) For $a = 30$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^2 + 30 = y^2. \quad \dots(3)$$

- (i) If we take $x_1 = 3$, $x_2 = 5$, $x_3 = 6$ and $y = 10$ then equation (3) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (3, 5, 6, 10)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 30 = y^2$.
- (ii) If we take $x_1 = 3$, $x_2 = 7$, $x_3 = 9$ and $y = 13$ then equation (3) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (3, 7, 9, 13)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 30 = y^2$.
- (iii) If we take $x_1 = 6$, $x_2 = 7$, $x_3 = 9$ and $y = 14$ then equation (3) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (6, 7, 9, 14)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 30 = y^2$.

- (iv) If we take $x_1 = 5, x_2 = 7, x_3 = 11$ and $y = 15$ then equation (3) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (5, 7, 11, 15)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 30 = y^2$.

(d) For $a = 40$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^2 + 40 = y^2. \quad \dots(4)$$

- (i) If we take $x_1 = 3$ and $y = 7$ then equation (4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, y) = (3, 7)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + 40 = y^2$.
- (ii) If we take $x_1 = 9$ and $y = 11$ then equation (8.4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, y) = (9, 11)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + 40 = y^2$.
- (iii) If we take $x_1 = 4, x_2 = 5$ and $y = 9$ then equation (4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (4, 5, 9)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 40 = y^2$.
- (iv) If we take $x_1 = 2, x_2 = 10$ and $y = 12$ then equation (4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (2, 10, 12)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 40 = y^2$.
- (v) If we take $x_1 = 2, x_2 = 9, x_3 = 10$ and $y = 15$ then equation (4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (2, 9, 10, 15)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 40 = y^2$.
- (vi) If we take $x_1 = 4, x_2 = 5, x_3 = 12$ and $y = 15$ then equation (4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (4, 5, 12, 15)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 40 = y^2$.
- (vii) If we take $x_1 = 6, x_2 = 7, x_3 = 10$ and $y = 15$ then equation (4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (6, 7, 10, 15)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 40 = y^2$.
- (viii) If we take $x_1 = 4, x_2 = 13$ and $y = 15$ then equation (4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (4, 13, 15)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 40 = y^2$.
- (ix) If we take $x_1 = 2, x_2 = 4, x_3 = 14$ and $y = 16$ then equation (4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (2, 4, 14, 16)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 40 = y^2$.
- (x) If we take $x_1 = 4, x_2 = 6, x_3 = 8, x_4 = 10$ and $y = 16$ then equation (8.4) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (4, 6, 8, 10, 16)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 + 40 = y^2$.

(e) For $a = 50$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^2 + 50 = y^2. \quad \dots(5)$$

- (i) If we take $x_1 = 5, x_2 = 11$ and $y = 14$ then equation (5) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (5, 11, 14)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 50 = y^2$.

(f) For $a = 60$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^2 + 60 = y^2. \quad \dots(6)$$

- (i) If we take $x_1 = 2, x_2 = 5, x_3 = 6$ and $y = 15$ then equation (8.6) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (2, 5, 6, 15)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + 60 = y^2$.
- (ii) If we take $x_1 = 4, x_2 = 6, x_3 = 7, x_4 = 8$ and $y = 15$ then equation (6) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (4, 6, 7, 8, 15)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 + 60 = y^2$.

(B) Diophantine equation $\sum x_i^3 + a = y^3$:

(a) For $a = 0$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 = y^3. \quad \dots(7)$$

If we take $x_1 = 3, x_2 = 4, x_3 = 5$ and $y = 6$ then equation (7) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (3, 4, 5, 6)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 = y^3.$$

(b) For $a = 1$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 1 = y^3. \quad \dots(8)$$

If we take $x_1 = 6, x_2 = 8$ and $y = 9$ then equation (8) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (6, 8, 9)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + 1 = y^3.$$

(c) For $a = 2$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 2 = y^3. \quad \dots(9)$$

If we take $x_1 = 5, x_2 = 6$ and $y = 7$ then equation (9) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, y) = (5, 6, 7)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + 2 = y^3.$$

(d) For $a = 16$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 16 = y^3. \quad \dots(10)$$

If we take $x_1 = 3, x_2 = 6, x_3 = 7, x_4 = 9$ and $y = 11$ then equation (10) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (3, 6, 7, 9, 11)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + x_4^3 + 16 = y^3.$$

(e) For $a = 17$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 17 = y^3. \quad \dots(11)$$

If we take $x_1 = 3, x_2 = 5, x_3 = 7$ and $y = 8$ then equation (11) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (3, 5, 7, 8)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + 17 = y^3.$$

(f) For $a = 18$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 18 = y^3. \quad \dots(12)$$

If we take $x_1 = 2, x_2 = 4, x_3 = 8, x_4 = 9$ and $y = 11$ then equation (12) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (2, 4, 8, 9, 11)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + x_4^3 + 16 = y^3.$$

(g) For $a = 20$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 20 = y^3. \quad \dots(13)$$

If we take $x_1 = 5, x_2 = 7, x_3 = 8$ and $y = 10$ then equation (8.12) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (5, 7, 8, 10)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + 17 = y^3.$$

(h) For $a = 20$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 20 = y^3. \quad \dots(14)$$

If we take $x_1 = 2, x_2 = 3, x_3 = 6, x_4 = 9$ and $y = 10$ then equation (14) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (2, 3, 6, 9, 10)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + x_4^3 + 16 = y^3.$$

(i) For $a = 30$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 30 = y^3. \quad \dots(15)$$

If we take $x_1 = 5, x_2 = 6, x_3 = 7$ and $y = 9$ then equation (15) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, y) = (5, 6, 7, 9)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + 17 = y^3.$$

(j) For $a = 50$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 50 = y^3. \quad \dots(16)$$

If we take $x_1 = 1, x_2 = 4, x_3 = 6, x_4 = 10$ and $y = 11$ then equation (16) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (1, 4, 6, 10, 11)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + x_4^3 + 16 = y^3.$$

(k) For $a = 55$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 55 = y^3. \quad \dots(17)$$

If we take $x_1 = 3, x_2 = 4, x_3 = 5, x_4 = 9$ and $y = 10$ then equation (17) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (3, 4, 5, 9, 10)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + x_4^3 + 16 = y^3.$$

(l) For $a = 55$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 55 = y^3. \quad \dots(18)$$

If we take $x_1 = 1, x_2 = 3, x_3 = 4, x_4 = 5, x_5 = 6, x_6 = 8$ and $y = 10$ then equation (18) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, y) = (1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + x_4^3 + x_5^3 + x_6^3 + 55 = y^3.$$

(m) For $a = 19$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 19 = y^3. \quad \dots(19)$$

If we take $x_1 = 2, x_2 = 3, x_3 = 7, x_4 = 11$ and $y = 12$ then equation (19) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (2, 3, 7, 11, 12)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + x_4^3 + 19 = y^3.$$

(n) For $a = 19$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 19 = y^3. \quad \dots(20)$$

If we take $x_1 = 5, x_2 = 7, x_3 = 8, x_4 = 9$ and $y = 12$ then equation (20) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (5, 7, 8, 9, 12)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + x_4^3 + 19 = y^3.$$

(o) For $a = 21$ the given Diophantine equation becomes

$$\sum x_i^3 + 21 = y^3. \quad \dots(21)$$

If we take $x_1 = 2, x_2 = 3, x_3 = 6, x_4 = 10$ and $y = 12$ then equation (22) is satisfied. Thus $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, y) = (2, 3, 6, 10, 12)$ is the solution of the Diophantine equation

$$x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3 + x_4^3 + 21 = y^3.$$

8.3 Concluding Remarks: Here the Diophantine equation $\sum x_i^2 + a = y^2$ has been discussed for $a = 10, 20, 30, 40, 50$ and 60 . Also the Diophantine equation $\sum x_i^3 + a = y^3$ has been discussed for $a = 0, 1, 2, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 30, 50$ and 55 . Possible solutions of these Diophantine equations have been obtained. These Diophantine equations can be discussed for other values of a .

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